

JusBR-ER: A Benchmark for Entity Resolution of Legal Concepts in Brazilian Portuguese

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence systems for law increasingly rely on structured knowledge — legal knowledge graphs (KGs) — to support retrieval, reasoning, and decision analysis across large volumes of case law. These KGs require entity resolution (ER) to determine whether two extracted concept names refer to the same legal notion — yet no benchmark for this task was found in any language. We introduce JusBR-ER, a 1,071-pair dataset of Brazilian legal concepts validated by a practicing lawyer, covering synonyms, writing variants, antonym traps, and genus–species distinctions. Using JusBR-ER, we diagnose a cascading pipeline under development and expose three architectural blind spots: (1) the Jaro–Winkler candidate threshold discards 76% of true merges before any semantic model sees them, capping recall at 24.2%; (2) the embedding auto-merge stage has $2.5\times$ more impact on precision than the LLM choice, yet operates without downstream review; (3) a 40-line rule-based qualifier guard outperforms both embedding models at detecting antonym false positives, with zero false negatives. Replacing the string-first cascade with embedding-first blocking raises F1 from 36.6% to 85.9%. A multi-dimensional scoring model that combines all signals into a learned function does not surpass the staged pipeline (F1 = 77.5%), confirming that the LLM’s value lies in full-text reasoning, not in a compressed scalar. We release the benchmark, annotation guidelines, a validated synonym dictionary of 487 legal concept pairs, and the qualifier guard.¹

1 Introduction

Legal knowledge graphs aggregate structured information from court decisions, enabling retrieval and reasoning at the concept level. A foundational requirement is *entity resolution* (ER): deter-

mining whether two extracted concept names — such as *periculum in mora* and *perigo de dano* — refer to the same legal notion. Unlike general-domain ER, where entities are typically proper nouns with stable spellings, legal concept ER faces terminological variation across Latin and vernacular forms, cross-code equivalences between successive statutes, and near-miss traps where a single qualifier inverts meaning (*boa-fé objetiva* vs. *boa-fé subjetiva*).

Despite the practical importance of legal ER, a systematic review of 71 benchmarks cataloged in two recent surveys (Liu et al., 2026; Premasiri et al., 2025) reveals a dual gap. First, entity resolution is absent as a task: all cataloged benchmarks address NER, judgment prediction, QA, summarization, or classification — none addresses ER of legal concepts in any language. Second, Brazilian Portuguese is severely under-represented: only 5 of 71 benchmarks (7%) cover pt-BR, all limited to NER and event detection, despite Brazil operating the world’s largest judiciary backlog with 80.6 million pending cases and a 99.6% digital filing rate (Conselho Nacional de Justiça, 2025).

The standard approach to ER uses a cascading pipeline: cheap string similarity metrics filter candidates, then progressively more expensive stages — embeddings and LLMs — classify the survivors (Christen, 2012; Papadakis et al., 2020). This architecture carries two implicit assumptions: (1) improving the expensive stages improves the pipeline, and (2) the expensive stages are where errors matter most. We evaluate a 4-stage cascade (normalization → Jaro–Winkler → embeddings → LLM) on JusBR-ER and show that both assumptions are wrong in the legal domain.

Our evaluation exposes three architectural blind spots. First, **Stage 2 (Jaro–Winkler) creates a recall ceiling**: at the default threshold of 0.88, 76% of true merge pairs are discarded before reaching any semantic model. Second, **Stage 3 (embed-**

¹Resources available at <https://github.com/sensdiego/jusbr-er>

dings) is an unaudited error source: it silently auto-merges pairs without LLM review, and the choice of embedding model has $2.5\times$ more impact on precision than the choice of LLM — yet the embedding stage is rarely ablated in ER literature. Third, **Stage 4 (LLM) is nearly perfect on the pairs it sees**, but sees only 24% of the dataset. Replacing the string-first cascade with embedding-first blocking raises F1 from 36.6% to 85.9% without changing any model.

Contributions. (1) We introduce JUSBR-ER, a 1,071-pair benchmark for entity resolution of legal concepts in Brazilian Portuguese — to our knowledge, the first such resource in any language (§3). (2) We quantify the cascade bottleneck: the Jaro–Winkler threshold dominates pipeline performance, and lowering it from 0.88 to 0.70 doubles F1 (§5.1). (3) We isolate the embedding auto-merge stage as the pipeline’s primary precision driver, showing that swapping Legal-BERTimbau for BGE-M3 cuts false positives by 56% (§5.3). (4) We show that a 40-line qualifier guard eliminates antonym false positives that both embedding models miss, with zero false negatives (§5.2). (5) We demonstrate that multi-dimensional scoring does not surpass the staged pipeline, confirming that the LLM’s value lies in full-text reasoning rather than in a compressed scalar signal (§5.4). (6) We release the benchmark, annotation guidelines, a validated synonym dictionary of 487 legal concept pairs, and the qualifier guard.

2 Related Work

Entity resolution. ER has been studied since Fellegi and Sunter (1969), with modern surveys by Elmagarmid et al. (2007) and Christophides et al. (2021). The cascading architecture — blocking followed by classification — is standard (Christen, 2012; Papadakis et al., 2020). Classic blocking strategies such as the sorted neighborhood method (Hernández and Stolfo, 1995) reduce the quadratic comparison space by sorting records on a key and comparing only within a sliding window — our Jaro–Winkler stage is a variant of this principle. Li et al. (2020) showed that fine-tuning pre-trained language models (BERT, RoBERTa) for entity matching as sequence-pair classification outperforms prior deep learning approaches by up to 29 F1 points on standard benchmarks, establishing the PLM-based paradigm that LLM-based matchers extend. Recent work explores

LLMs for pair classification, demonstrating strong results on benchmarks such as Magellan (Mudgal et al., 2018; Peeters and Bizer, 2023; Peeters et al., 2025). Smith et al. (2026) release OpenSanctions Pairs, a 755K-pair benchmark for ER of sanctioned persons and organizations, showing that LLMs reach 98.95% F1 versus 91.33% for rule-based matchers — a pattern consistent with our findings. However, existing ER benchmarks are drawn almost exclusively from e-commerce and bibliographic domains (Köpcke et al., 2010; Peeters et al., 2023). No benchmark targets legal concepts in any language, and the interaction between blocking thresholds and downstream model accuracy has received little empirical attention.

Legal NLP. Recent surveys catalog over 70 benchmarks for legal AI tasks including NER, judgment prediction, QA, and document classification (Liu et al., 2026; Premasiri et al., 2025), yet neither survey mentions entity resolution. For Brazilian Portuguese, foundational resources include LeNER-Br for named entity recognition (Luz de Araujo et al., 2018), UlyssesNER-Br for legislative NER (Albuquerque et al., 2022), and Labor Lex for relation extraction in labor courts (de Castro and Silva, 2025). Domain-adapted language models include BERTimbau (Souza et al., 2020), Legal-BERTimbau (Polo et al., 2021), RoBERTaLexPT (Garcia et al., 2024), Sabiá (Almeida et al., 2024), and Juru (Malaquias Junior et al., 2024). On the knowledge graph side, Pires et al. (2022) construct a 214K-node Brazilian legal KG from legislation, and de Martim (2025) propose ontology-driven RAG over legal norms. The closest related work is LexRel (Cai et al., 2025), a benchmark for legal relation extraction in Chinese civil cases — a different task (RE, not ER) in a different legal system. **JUSBR-ER is, to our knowledge, the first benchmark specifically targeting entity resolution of legal concepts.**

Embedding models and antonymy. Embedding models are known to struggle with negation and antonymy, encoding antonym pairs as near-identical vectors (Mikolov et al., 2013; Mrkšić et al., 2016). Counter-fitting (Mrkšić et al., 2016) addresses this via post-hoc constraint injection, but requires curated antonym lists. In the legal domain, this problem is acute: domain-specific models trained for semantic similarity score *boa-fé objetiva* and *boa-fé subjetiva* at cosine 0.97 — above typical auto-merge thresholds — because

Source	n	Rationale
SAME_AS sample	200	Audit existing links
Near-miss JW	193	Probe blind zone
Emb-high / JW-low	150	Test embedding value
Latin/Port. equiv.	143	Cross-lang. synonyms
Active learning	199	Disagreement pairs
Prior dataset	186	Migration from v1
Total (dedup)	1,071	530 / 541 merge

Table 1: Pair generation strategies. The stratified design overrepresents hard cases for pipeline calibration, not population-level estimation.

antonyms co-occur in the same legal contexts. Our qualifier guard takes a simpler approach: instead of fixing the embedding space, it intercepts antonym pairs before they reach it. Recent multilingual models like BGE-M3 (Xiao et al., 2024) show improved antonym separation, which we confirm empirically.

3 Dataset: JusBR-ER

3.1 Source

Our benchmark is derived from a legal knowledge graph under active development by sens.legal, a Brazilian legal data infrastructure project that uses AI for retrieval and reasoning over case law. The KG contains 14,751 legal concept nodes (*Criterio*), 5,270 statutory provision nodes (*DispositivoLegal*), and 6,271 SAME_AS relationships created by HDBSCAN clustering followed by LLM classification. The KG aggregates decisions from three Brazilian courts (STJ, TJPR, TJSP). All entity links were created algorithmically and had never been validated by a legal expert prior to this work — an audit of 200 randomly sampled SAME_AS edges revealed a 48.5% error rate, motivating the construction of JUSBR-ER.

3.2 Pair Generation

We generated pairs through six strategies designed to probe different failure modes of the ER pipeline:

3.3 Annotation

All 1,071 pairs were validated by the first author — a practicing lawyer registered with the Brazilian Bar Association (OAB/PR 96,036) — through a binary decision: “Should these two concepts be represented as a single node in the knowledge graph?” Annotation guidelines with four borderline rulings were established before labeling,

Type (pt-BR)	Type (EN)	Merge?
identico	identical	Yes
sinonimo	synonym	Yes
variante	writing variant	Yes
genero_especie	genus-species	No
esp_mesmo_genero	same-genus siblings	No
ant_complementar	compl. antonym	No
sem_relacao	unrelated	No

Table 2: Relationship taxonomy. Three types result in merge; four result in no_merge.

covering cases such as genus-species distinctions (*tutela provisória* \supset *tutela de urgência*) and scope-altering qualifiers (*boa-fé objetiva* \neq *boa-fé subjetiva*).

Intra-annotator agreement. To measure annotation consistency, the annotator re-labeled 100 randomly selected pairs (seed 42) without access to the original decisions. Cohen’s κ between the original and re-annotation was 0.87 (near-perfect agreement). Six residual disagreements involve boundary cases — metalinguistic qualifiers (*necessidade de*), scope distinctions (*erro material* as autonomous hypothesis), and context specificity (*liminar possessória* vs. generic *periculum in mora*) — suggesting these edge cases should be addressed in future guideline revisions.

3.4 Relationship Taxonomy

We define seven relationship types organized by merge decision:

4 Method

4.1 Cascading Pipeline

The pipeline processes entity pairs through four stages:

Stage 1: Normalization. Lowercase, accent removal, legal abbreviation expansion (art. \rightarrow artigo, CPC \rightarrow código de processo civil), Roman \rightarrow Arabic numeral conversion.

Stage 2: Jaro-Winkler. JW similarity on normalized strings. $JW \geq 0.95 \rightarrow$ auto-merge (skip stages 3–4). $JW \in [T, 0.95) \rightarrow$ candidate (proceed to stage 3). $JW < T \rightarrow$ reject. A numeric guard blocks pairs whose number sets differ.

Stage 3: Embeddings. Sentence embeddings encode candidates. $\text{Cosine} \geq 0.92 \rightarrow$ auto-merge (skip stage 4). Below \rightarrow proceed to stage 4. We evaluate two embedding models:

Model	Provider	Role
Claude Sonnet 4.6	Anthropic	LLM
Kimi K2 (~1T MoE)	Groq	LLM
Llama-3.3-70B	Groq	LLM
Legal-BERTimbau-sts	Local	Embedding
BGE-M3	Local	Embedding

Table 3: Models evaluated. All LLMs use the same prompt and three-vote majority protocol.

Legal-BERTimbau-sts-base (Polo et al., 2021), a 768-dim Portuguese legal model, and BGE-M3 (Xiao et al., 2024), a 1,024-dim multilingual model.

Stage 4: LLM. Three-vote majority classification with structured JSON output.

4.2 Qualifier Guard

A rule-based pre-filter that blocks pairs differing only by an opposite qualifier. The implementation checks the symmetric difference of word sets against 11 antonym concepts (19 entries including masculine/feminine variants):

```
_OPPOSITE_QUALIFIERS = [
    {"objetivo", "subjetivo"},
    {"moral", "material"},
    {"absoluta", "relativa"},
    {"positiva", "negativa"},
    {"direta", "indireta"},
    # ... 10 more pairs
]

def qualifiers_differ(a, b):
    diff = set(a.split()) ^ set(b.split())
    return any(diff <= p
               for p in _OPPOSITE_QUALIFIERS)
```

If the only words that differ between two entity names form an antonym pair, the entities are blocked from merging regardless of their JW or embedding scores.

4.3 Models

4.4 Metrics

Precision, recall, F1, and accuracy with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals (2,000 resamples, seed 42).

5 Results

5.1 The Recall Ceiling

At the default threshold (JW=0.88), the pipeline partitions 1,071 pairs into three groups:

A threshold sweep confirms the effect is monotonic:

Partition	Pairs	%	Merges
Below threshold	765	71.4	372
Numeric guard	45	4.2	30
Candidates	261	24.4	128

Table 4: Pair partition at JW=0.88. 765 pairs (71.4%) are rejected at Stage 2, trapping 372 true merges. Recall ceiling: 24.2%.

JW	P	R	F1	Δ F1
0.95	90.6	10.9	19.5	-12.9
0.88	49.0	24.2	32.4	—
0.80	57.1	56.6	56.9	+24.5
0.70	55.2	81.9	66.0	+33.6

Table 5: JW threshold sweep (JW-only mode). Lowering from 0.88 to 0.70 doubles F1. The optimal design is aggressive candidate generation followed by precise semantic filtering.

5.2 Rule Beats Model for Qualifiers

Six pairs in the dataset share identical words except for a single qualifier pair. Table 6 shows that with Legal-BERTimbau, two pairs exceed the auto-merge threshold (cosine ≥ 0.92) and are merged silently — no LLM ever reviews them. BGE-M3 scores all six below the threshold, but at lower thresholds two would still pass. The qualifier guard blocks all six regardless of embedding model or threshold, with zero false negatives on 1,071 pairs.

5.3 The Silent Stage: Embedding Model Matters More Than LLM

The embedding auto-merge stage (Stage 3) operates without LLM oversight. We ablate the embedding model while holding the LLM constant:

The root cause is auto-merge volume: BERTimbau auto-merges 68 pairs (35 incorrect), BGE-M3 auto-merges 38 (11 incorrect).

5.4 Embedding-First Blocking and Multi-Dimensional Scoring

The cascade bottleneck suggests an inverted architecture: aggressive candidate generation via embeddings, followed by LLM classification. We replace the JW gate with a BGE-M3 cosine threshold of 0.70:

We then test whether a multi-dimensional scoring model can surpass the staged pipeline by combining all available signals — JW score, token Jaccard overlap, BGE-M3 cosine, qualifier guard, numeric guard, and LLM merge votes — into a sin-

Pair (abbreviated)	JW	Bert	BGE
Boa-fé obj. / subj.	.96	.97	.81
Crit. obj. / subj. p/ termo	.95	.96	.80
Dano moral / material	.93	.89	.72
Tutela urg. / evidência	.93	.91	.78
Honor. sucumb. / contr.	.90	.85	.68
Honor. advoc. / sucumb.	.91	.93	.76

Table 6: Qualifier-antonym pairs. All are true no_merge. BERTimbau auto-merges two (cosine \geq 0.92); the qualifier guard blocks all six with zero false negatives.

Configuration	P	R	F1
Sonnet + BERTimbau	75.7	24.2	36.6
Sonnet + BGE-M3	87.7	24.2	37.9
Kimi K2 + BERTimbau	71.0	22.6	34.3
Kimi K2 + BGE-M3	79.9	21.7	34.1
Llama 70B + BERTimbau	71.1	21.3	32.8

Table 7: Embedding ablation. Swapping BERTimbau \rightarrow BGE-M3 improves precision by +12.0pp (Sonnet), while swapping LLM improves only +4.7pp. The embedding model has **2.5 \times more impact** on precision than the LLM. 95% bootstrap CIs (2,000 re-samples): Sonnet+BGE-M3 P=[82.2, 92.8] vs. Sonnet+BERTimbau P=[69.0, 82.1] — CIs do not overlap, confirming statistical significance.

gle learned function:

The LLM’s value in the staged pipeline comes from full-text reasoning; compressing this into a scalar (merge votes / 3) discards the reasoning that makes the LLM superior.

5.5 Active Learning as Diagnostic

Batch 5 of the dataset (199 pairs) was generated by selecting pairs where the current pipeline and Claude Sonnet disagreed on classification:

These are pairs where string similarity says one thing and semantics say another: high JW but different concept (*aplicação do CDC* vs. *aplicabilidade do CDC*, JW=0.93, no_merge), or low JW but same concept (*contrariedade ao agravo* vs. *contraminuta*, JW=0.52, merge). The diagnostic exposes the fundamental limitation of string-first pipelines: **lexical similarity is a poor proxy for conceptual identity when the domain has rich synonymy and near-miss traps.**

5.6 The Synonym Dictionary as Bypass

From the 530 validated merge pairs, 487 have distinct normalized forms. These 487 pairs form a validated synonym dictionary — a lookup table that bypasses all four pipeline stages for known

Method	P	R	F1
Full cascade	87.7	24.2	37.9
Emb-first + Sonnet	94.4	78.9	85.9

Table 8: Embedding-first blocking. F1 jumps from 37.9% to 85.9% — a 2.3 \times improvement — without changing any model. 95% bootstrap CIs: emb-first F1=[83.4, 88.1] vs. cascade F1=[33.1, 42.4] — CIs do not overlap on any metric.

Model	P	R	F1
LogReg (6 features)	75.5	79.6	77.5
GBT (6 features)	74.9	78.1	76.5
LogReg (no LLM)	60.6	70.6	65.2
GBT (no LLM)	64.1	63.4	63.8

Table 9: Multi-dimensional scoring (5-fold CV). The scoring model does not surpass the staged pipeline (77.5% vs. 85.9%). Feature importance: BGE-M3 cosine (36.2%) > LLM vote (29.4%) > JW score (23.0%).

pairs with 100% accuracy. At the KG’s current scale (\sim 14K entity types), an estimated 15% of candidate pairs match known synonyms, eliminating one embedding computation and up to three LLM API calls per hit. The dictionary is a living artifact: each entity resolution run that includes human validation extends it, creating a flywheel where use improves the dictionary and the dictionary improves use.

6 Discussion

Generalizability. Our finding — that the cheapest stage dominates pipeline performance — is likely not specific to legal ER. Any cascading pipeline where the first stage uses a metric with poor domain alignment and the later stages have significantly higher accuracy will exhibit the same recall ceiling. Candidate domains include biomedical ER (drug names, gene aliases), multilingual ER (transliteration variants), and technical standards (specification codes across versions).

When rules beat models. The qualifier guard’s success raises a broader question: when should ER systems use rules instead of models? Our data suggests a heuristic: use rules when the error class is defined by a finite, enumerable set of discrete features (in this case, 11 antonym concepts); use models when the error class requires open-ended semantic understanding. Rules and models are complementary — the guard handles errors that

Method	Accuracy
Pipeline (JW + emb + Llama-8B)	12.0%
Claude Sonnet 4.6	88.0%

Table 10: Active learning diagnostic. On disagreement pairs, the pipeline scores worse than random; Sonnet achieves 88% — a $7.3\times$ gap.

embeddings systematically miss, while the LLM handles errors that rules cannot enumerate.

Cost of embedding-first blocking. The embedding-first pipeline requires $6.6\times$ more LLM calls (2,562 vs. 390 three-vote classifications), but the marginal cost per F1 point gained is small: a 48pp F1 improvement for a $6.6\times$ budget increase, or equivalently, each additional F1 point costs $\sim 14\%$ more API budget.² The cascade’s apparent savings are illusory because its recall ceiling renders most of the budget ineffective. At production scale, the synonym dictionary bypass (§5.6) would offset part of this increase by eliminating LLM calls for the estimated 15% of pairs that match known synonyms.

The audit gap in cascading pipelines. Our embedding ablation reveals an underappreciated property of cascading architectures: stages that bypass downstream review create unaudited error channels. When the embedding stage auto-merges a pair with cosine ≥ 0.92 , no LLM reviews the decision. This has implications beyond ER — any multi-stage system with early-exit paths (RAG pipelines with confidence thresholds, classification cascades, routing architectures) may harbor similar blind spots. The remedy is straightforward: independently evaluate each early-exit path, not just the end-to-end pipeline.

7 Future Work

Two directions emerge from this work. First, **contradiction detection as prompt strategy**: recent work on entity matching in sanctions data (Smith et al., 2026) shows that framing ER as “find contradictions between records” outperforms similarity-based prompts. Our qualifier guard is a rule-based instance of this principle — generalizing it to the LLM prompt may improve precision on hard pairs. Second, **dataset expansion**: JUSBR-ER covers

²At March 2026 Claude Sonnet pricing (\$3/M input, \$15/M output), the full-benchmark cost is \$11.53 (emb-first) vs. \$1.76 (cascade).

1,071 pairs from three courts (STJ, TJPR, TJSP). Extending coverage to additional courts, statutory provisions, and doctrinal concepts would increase both scale and domain diversity.

8 Limitations

JUSBR-ER contains 1,071 pairs, smaller than record-level benchmarks such as OpenSanctions Pairs (755K). The difference reflects the annotation cost: each pair requires domain expertise in Brazilian law, as the decision depends on juridical reasoning rather than field matching. Single annotator; intra-annotator agreement is $\kappa = 0.87$ on 100 re-labeled pairs (§3.3). The stratified sampling design intentionally overrepresents hard cases — population-level error rates require a separate random sample. We evaluated three LLMs and two embedding models; fine-tuned models and other multilingual embeddings were not compared. The pipeline was evaluated pair-by-pair; production effects such as transitivity and cluster coherence were not measured. The benchmark was designed to probe failure modes of a specific pipeline; findings may not transfer to architecturally different ER systems.

Ethics Statement

JusBR-ER is derived from publicly available Brazilian court decisions, which are public records under Brazilian law (Art. 93, IX, Constitution). The dataset contains only legal concept names (e.g., “dano moral”, “boa-fé objetiva”) — no personally identifiable information, case facts, or party names are included. The annotation was performed by the first author in a professional capacity; no crowdsourcing or undisclosed labor was involved.

9 Conclusion

We introduced JUSBR-ER, to our knowledge the first benchmark for entity resolution of legal concepts in any language. Evaluating a cascading ER pipeline on 1,071 human-validated pairs, we found that the cheapest stage — string similarity — is the performance bottleneck, not the expensive LLM. Three findings stand out: (1) the Jaro-Winkler threshold creates a recall ceiling that no downstream model can overcome — lowering it from 0.88 to 0.70 doubles F1; (2) the embedding auto-merge stage has $2.5\times$ more impact on precision than the LLM choice, yet operates without

review; (3) a 40-line qualifier guard outperforms both embedding models at detecting antonym false positives. Replacing the string-first cascade with embedding-first blocking raises F1 from 36.6% to 85.9%, while a multi-dimensional scoring approach confirms that the LLM’s value lies in full-text reasoning, not in compressed features. We release the benchmark, annotation guidelines, synonym dictionary, and qualifier guard at <https://github.com/sensdiego/jusbr-er>.

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